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Literary and philosophical analysis of ‘‘ Never let me go’’

Abstract

This article provides a detailed analysis of content, artistic features and philosophical ideas of the novel ‘‘Never let me go’’. The novel explores the value of human life, love, friendship, fate and ethical responsibility of society through the concept of cloning. The author uses a calm and simple narrative style of encourage deep reflection and reveal the essence of humanity.

Keywords:

Literary work, cloning, humanity, love, friendship, fate, donation, ethical issues, society, freedom, memory.

Introduction

Literature plays an important role in understanding human life and its meaning. The novel ‘‘Never let me ‘‘ go is one of the most significant work in modern English literature. It was written by Kazuo Ishiguro and presents deep issues of humanity, ethics and society through elements of science fiction.

In today’s world the rapid development of technology, especially in fields like biotechnology and cloning raises new questions about the value of human life. From this perspective, the novel can be considered not only a literary work but also a subject of social and philosophical analysis.

The main aim of this article is to analyze the novel in detail, explain its key ideas and describe the author’s artistic style.

Discussion

The story is narrated by Kathy H. ,who remembers her childhood at a special place called Hailsham. At first, the school seems safe and protective but gradually it is revealed that the students are clones raised to become organ donors. This truth forms the central conflict of the novel.

One of the unique aspects of Hailsham is the importance given to art and creativity. Students are encouraged to draw and express spiritually human. The idea of the ‘‘Gallery’’ is especially important, as it reflects their inner world.

Later the characters move to the Cottages, where they begin to live more independently. During this time, they start to think seriously about their future. The relationships between Kathy, Ruth and Tommy become more complex. Feelings such as hidden love, jealousy and emotional conflict are described in a realistic way. Another important feature of the novel is that it is told through memories. Kathy narrates her past, which makes the story more subjective and emotional. The reader does not only follow the events but also feels them deeply. The character’s attitude toward their fate is also significant. They do not actively resist their destiny but accept it. This raises questions about freedom, social, control and the power of the system.

In addition, love and friendship play a central role in the novel. Even in difficult circumstances, the characters maintain their emotions. This highlights one of the most important aspects of humanity.

In conclusion, Never let me go is a novel that encourages deep reflection on human life and its value. Through the idea of cloning, the author presents important ethical issues and explores the meaning of humanity. Themes such as love, friendship

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and fate are expressed in a natural and emotional way. Moreover, the character's attitude toward their destiny makes the reader think deeply.

Although they cannot change their fate, they manage to preserve their human emotions, which is one of the key ideas of the novel. Overall, this novel is not only interesting as a literary work but also significant from philosophical and ethical perspectives. It leaves a strong impression on the reader and encourages serious reflection on life.

Conclusion

To sum up, "Never let me go" is a novel that encourages deep thinking about human life and its value. It presents themes of love, friendship and fate in a powerful way. The novel is not only interesting but also philosophically important.

References

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